

Effects of zinc fertilization on physical grain quality of basmati rice

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Physical grain quality in aromatic basmati rice has achieved great attention in recent years due to heavy foreign demand and increased exports. During 2003-04, 771,000 t of Basmati rice was exported from India (GOI 2004). No information on the effect of nutrient management on the physical grain quality of basmati rice before and after cooking is currently available. This study aims to bridge that gap. This information is also needed amid the rising demand for organic food (Prasad 2005) and the widespread concern that fertilizers have a harmful effect on food quality.

To study the effects of zinc fertilization on some aspects of physical quality, grain samples were obtained from the fields

at IARI. The experiment aimed to assess the relative efficiency of zinc oxide- and zinc sulfate-coated (at 0.5%, 1.0%, 1.5%, and 2.0%) urea, uncoated urea, and a no-zinc (only N through urea) control. The experiment was conducted in a randomized block design with three replications. All plots received 120 kg N ha⁻¹ as urea. Zinc sulfate- and zinc-oxide-coated urea were obtained from Indo-Gulf Fertilizers Ltd., Jagdishpur, India. Soil in the experimental field was a sandy clay loam with pH 8.2, 0.54% organic C, and medium fertility with respect to P and K. DTPA-extractable (Lindsay and Norvell 1978) zinc in soil was 0.68 mg kg⁻¹ weight of soil. Rice quality parameters were studied follow-

ing the methods described by Dela Cruz and Khush (2000). The basmati rice variety used in this study was Pusa Sugandh 5 (Pusa 3A/Haryana Basmati), which was recently developed at IARI and has been cultivated in the northwestern rice-wheat cropping system of the country.

Pusa Sugandh 5 has extra long and slender grains (Jennings et al 1979). Zinc fertilization with 2.0% zinc oxide- or zinc sulfate-coated urea significantly increased hulling percentage in rice compared with that treated with uncoated urea. Zinc coating of urea had no significant effect on grain length before cooking, but, after cooking, grains treated with 1.0%, 1.5%, and 2.0% ZnSO₄ coating were significantly longer than those ob-

Grain quality parameters of Pusa Sugandh 5 as influenced by zinc fertilization.

Treatment	Hulling (%)	Grain length before cooking (mm)	Grain breadth before cooking (mm)	L/B ^a before cooking	Grain length after cooking (mm)	Grain breadth after cooking (mm)	L/B ^a after cooking	L ₁ :L ₂ ^b	B ₁ :B ₂ ^c
Prilled urea	64.7	7.6	1.4	5.5	12.8	2.0	6.4	1.69	1.47
0.5% ZnO-coated urea	68.1	7.8	1.5	5.2	13.5	2.1	6.4	1.72	1.44
0.5% ZnSO ₄ -coated urea	68.2	7.9	1.6	4.9	13.6	2.2	6.2	1.72	1.39
1.0% ZnO-coated urea	68.9	7.8	1.6	4.9	13.7	2.2	6.2	1.74	1.39
1.0% ZnSO ₄ -coated urea	69.5	8.0	1.7	4.7	13.9	2.3	6.0	1.74	1.36
1.5% ZnO-coated urea	69.9	7.8	1.6	4.9	13.6	2.3	6.0	1.74	1.43
1.5% ZnSO ₄ -coated urea	70.8	8.0	1.7	4.7	13.9	2.3	5.9	1.74	1.38
2.0% ZnO-coated urea	73.0	7.9	1.6	4.9	13.6	2.3	5.9	1.73	1.43
2.0% ZnSO ₄ -coated urea	74.5	8.1	1.8	4.5	14.3	2.4	6.0	1.76	1.33
CD (P=0.05)	6.4	ns	0.2	0.9	1.0	0.2	ns	ns	0.12

^aL/B: length-breadth ratio. ^bL₁:L₂ = ratio of grain length before (L₁) to that after cooking (L₂). ^cB₁:B₂ = ratio of grain breadth before cooking (B₁) to that after (B₂) cooking.

tained with urea alone. For grain breadth, treatments with 1.0%, 1.5%, and 2.0% ZnSO₄-coated urea had bolder grains before and after cooking. Coating prilled urea with ZnO at 1.5% and 2.0% gave significantly bolder grains than prilled urea only after cooking. Upon cooking, grain length increased by 1.69 to 1.76 times that of the grain before cooking, but the effect of coating prilled urea with zinc was not significant. Similarly, grain breadth increased by 1.33 to 1.47 times (see table). The grains obtained with 2.0%

ZnSO₄-coated urea were significantly thinner (considered a good quality trait) than those obtained with prilled urea. It is therefore concluded that zinc fertilization had no deleterious effects on the quality of basmati rice; it even increased hulling percentage and produced longer and better grains.

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BRRi dhan 47: a salt-tolerant variety for the boro season

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The demand for a salt-tolerant rice variety for the salinity-prone areas of Bangladesh during the boro season has long been felt. Three environmental constraints—saline soil, saline irrigation water, and cold temperature—have made this environment very complex. On-station replication of such an environment is thus very difficult. An alternative approach used participatory variety selection (PVS) under a mother-and-baby trial in 200 farmers' fields in salinity-prone areas of Bangladesh. The farmers had chosen four genotypes—PVS-B3, PVS-B8, PVS-B9, and PVS-B1—from 385 BR and IR lines with different degrees of salt tolerance.

Salt stress screening of the four PVS-B genotypes was done under controlled conditions. Of these genotypes, PVS-B3, PVS-B9, and PVS-B19 showed a very high degree of seedling-stage tolerance at 12–14 dS m⁻¹ (Fig. 1).

It should be noted that popular boro variety BRRi dhan 28 could tolerate salt stress at 4.0 dS m⁻¹ only. The same set of four PVS-B lines was screened for adult plant resistance to salt stress at 6.0 dS m⁻¹. Salinity was applied

at transplanting and was continued throughout the crop growth period. BRRi dhan 28 died 30 d after transplanting; PVS-B8 and PVS-B9 soon followed. PVS-B3 and PVS-B19 survived and flowered at 6.0 dS m⁻¹ (Fig. 2).

Fig. 1. Salt stress tolerance of BRRi dhan 47 at 12 dS m⁻¹ at the seedling stage. V1 = PVS-B3 (BRRi dhan 47), V2 = PVS-B8, IR29 = susceptible check, BRRi dhan 28 = standard check, V3 = PVS-B9, and V4 = PVS-B19.